

ANALYSIS THORACIC AORTIC ANEURYSM CTA SCANS USING SPATIAL STATISTIC

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Abstract *This study leverages spatial statistics to analyze the spatial distribution of the aorta, aiming to better understand the biomechanical behavior of Ascending Thoracic Aortic Aneurysms (ATAA) and its impact on clinical outcomes. CTA angiography was performed on 87 ATAA patients. Experimental variograms were computed for various variables, such as maximum diameter, from which key parameters of interest were extracted. These parameters were then analyzed over time to assess temporal patterns. The goal of this analysis was to identify whether similar patterns or behaviors emerge in features from CTA scans of patients with aneurysms of similar sizes, ultimately aiming to statistically validate the quality of the CTA scans.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Ascending Thoracic Aortic Aneurysm (ATAA) is a degenerative process of the thoracic aorta and a severe vascular disease characterized by the progressive dilation of the thoracic aorta due to the weakening of the aortic wall. The structure and function of the aorta can be affected by factors such as age, genetic, and lifestyle factors [1][2]. Aneurysm is one of the most common diseases associated with the aorta, and its rupture is a major cause of mortality in adults over 65 years old [3].

The aneurysm size is determined based on diameter measurements, which may slightly vary depending on the imaging technology used, such as ultrasound or computed tomography angiography (CTA). According to studies, elective repair is recommended when the maximum diameter (Dmax) exceeds 55 mm or when the lesion grows more than 1 cm per year [4]. However, it has been observed that these parameters are not sufficient, as there are cases of patients with maximum diameters smaller than the indicated threshold who experience aneurysm rupture, as well as cases of patients with larger diameters who do not experience rupture [5][6].

This study presents an exploratory analysis of the characteristics of ATAAs in a sample of patients using spatial statistics. Specifically, the variogram and the parameters sill and range are used to characterize the maximum diameters of the ascending aortas obtained from CTA angiography scans.

2. METHODS

2.1. Data

The dataset used in this study consists of several variables collected from 87 patients. Each patient contains variables that vary in spatial and temporal dimensions. Spatially, the variables are measured in equally distributed rings across the centerline, and temporally, representing different instances of the cardiac cycle measured in 5% increments associated with a time step in the cine CTA. The variable selected for this analysis was the maximum diameter of the ring at the given time point in millimeters. The data allows temporal analysis to observe and measure changes in the recorded parameters. The analysis presented in this work focuses on three patients, as they represent three distinct patient groups discussed in Section 3.2.

2.2 Empirical Variogram and Model Fitting

The variogram is a tool from geostatistics that allows analyzing the spatial relationship present in the data. To define it, it is necessary to define the regionalized variable [7][8]. A regionalized variable is a random variable for each region used. It is denoted by:

$$\{Z(s): s \in D \subset R^n\}.$$

Each $Z(s)$ is a random variable. The variogram γ is defined as:

$$\gamma(h) = \frac{1}{2} E \left[(Z(s) - Z(s + h))^2 \right]$$

where h is the vector (distance and direction) separating the values of the points. The variogram γ can be estimated by the empirical variogram $\hat{\gamma}$, defined as:

$$\hat{\gamma}(h) = \frac{1}{2|N(h)|} \sum_{(i,j) \in N(h)} (Z(i) - Z(j))^2$$

where $N(h) = \{(i,j): \|i - j\| = h\}$, that is, the number of pairs with separation vector h .

Figure 1: Theoretical model of variogram.

The variogram is a tool in geostatistics that captures spatial patterns in data. It stores information about how the properties of data change with distance and direction between sample points. The variogram helps to identify spatial relationships, revealing trends or uniformities in the data. It can be used to classify areas with similar behaviors. This ability to detect spatial patterns makes the variogram useful not only in geostatistics but also in any data analysis where spatial structure is important, helping to better understand and model the phenomena being studied.

Once the empirical variogram has been calculated, model fitting can be performed using well-known parametric models. In this work, the skgstat library in Python will be used, which provides a variety of variogram models [7][9] such as

- *Spherical*: This model describes a gradual increase in variability with distance, until it stabilizes at a maximum range.

- *Exponential*: The exponential model describes variability that increases continuously and more rapidly with distance.
- *Gaussian*: Similar to the exponential model but with a smoother decrease.
- *Matern*: This model is a generalization of the previous ones and includes an additional parameter that controls the smoothness of the function.
- *Stable*: The stable model is used for phenomena that show irregular variability, even at large distances.
- *Cubic*: Variability increases or decreases cubically with distance.

2.2 Data processing

The data processing for this study involved the calculation of experimental variograms for each patient, with measurements taken at multiple time points. In this work, only the maximum diameters were considered, which were used to assess spatial dependencies and quantify variability across different distances. The following steps were carried out to compute the variogram and its parameters:

1. *Data collection*: For each patient, the data was read from their corresponding file. Each dataset contained a series of observations taken over time, which included various spatial measurements of the region of interest. These data points served as the foundation for the subsequent analysis.
2. *Distance setup*: A predefined set of distances, ranging from 0 to 19 units, was selected to characterize the spatial relationship between the measurement points. These distances represent the intervals over which the differences in the data points were calculated and compared.
3. *Variogram calculation*: For each observation, the experimental variogram was computed using the selected distances. The variogram quantifies the spatial correlation between the measurements at different distances by calculating the squared differences between the values and their spatial lag. The variogram also provides insights into the spatial structure and dependencies of the data.
4. *Parameter estimation*: In addition to calculating the experimental variogram, key parameters of the variogram model were estimated. Twenty experimental variograms were calculated (one for each time point: 0%, 5%, 10%, etc.) for each patient. Then, the models mentioned in the previous subsection were used to construct 20 theoretical variograms for each patient with each model. The goal was to determine which model best fits the experimental variograms for each patient (Figure 2). To achieve this, the Normalized Root Mean Squared Error (NRMSE) was calculated for each patient and each model. NRMSE is a metric used to assess the accuracy of a model's predictions while accounting for the scale of the data. It is a variation of the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) but normalized to make it more interpretable across different datasets [10].

As a result, each patient had 20 NRMSE values per model. These NRMSE values were then averaged to determine which model best fit the data for each patient, and the model with the lowest average was selected as the best fit for that patient. Finally, a database was created, listing each patient along with the best fitting model and the parameters. These parameters include:

- *Nugget*: This parameter represents the small-scale variation or noise in the data, typically reflecting measurement error or fine-scale variability. It corresponds to the value of the variogram at distance zero.
- *Sill*: The sill represents the plateau level of the variogram, indicating the point at which the spatial correlation between measurements becomes negligible, and further increases in distance no longer influence the variance.
- *Range*: The range is the distance at which the variogram reaches the sill, indicating the effective spatial distance over which measurements are correlated.

Figure 2: Selection of the model that best fits based on the NRMSE for patient 5 at time 0. For this patient the best model is “stable”.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Analysis of the Empirical Variogram

The first observation is that the variogram is a useful tool for identifying patient groups. Initially, a group of patients was identified whose variogram exhibits an increasing trend (Figure 3). This suggests that the aneurysm is located at one of the extremes of the studied area or, less commonly, tends to concentrate towards one of those extremes.

Figure 3: Empirical variograms for patient 5.

On the other hand, the following variogram (Figure 4) shows a curvature at medium distances, which may indicate that the aneurysm is located at the center of the ascending aorta.

Figure 4: Empirical variograms for patient 4.

This confirms that the variogram preserves the spatial information of the aneurysm in the aorta; however, this is not such a relevant finding since it is easy to observe with tomography and by measuring the maximum diameters.

It can also be observed that there are important threshold values. It could be said that from 0 to 15, the variogram can be considered constant, which would indicate a uniform distribution along the ascending aorta. Values between 15 and 120 could be considered indicative of a more notable or evident aneurysm, depending on the previously discussed groups. Finally, values between 120 and 200 could indicate corrupted data. Regarding the latter, there were instances where some corrupted data were found, which were subsequently corrected.

3.2. Analysis of the variograms parameters

Once the variogram model is set for each patient, a range study is conducted, as it can provide information on elasticity or deformation depending on the distance [9]. This is because the range indicates how much influence one sample has over another (correlated measures) and the sill gives the trend of the variogram for distances quite large. An explanation will be given regarding the interpretation of the range and sill over time.

If the range is low, this suggests that the aorta does not easily propagate its deformation during systole, which may indicate local stiffness. If the range is high, the deformation of the aorta propagates over a greater distance, which may suggest a more elastic aorta, contributing to the propagation of deformation at higher ranges. That is, if one part of the aorta deforms, this deformation influences more distant sections. This is a typical behavior of a structure with low resistance to stress and a high capacity to distribute tensions.

There are cases where both high and low ranges may occur over time. This could indicate a time-dependent elastic response. If the fluctuations follow a pattern, it may be possible to analyze whether the aorta shows signs of fatigue or stress depending on time.

Now, the sill and range of some particular cases of patients will be analyzed. First, we will look at patient 2 who have small aneurysms but large deformations (Figure 5). Then, patient 18, who have large aneurysms (Figure 6). Finally, patient 30 who have small aneurysms with minor deformations (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Patient 2: sill and range (top); and aneurysm deformation of the ascending aorta (bottom) throughout the cardiac cycle.

In the case of patient 2, despite having a small aneurysm, there is low variability (see sill, Figure 5) due to the large deformation. Additionally, the variability fluctuates, indicating that the aorta exhibits some complexity in its structure. On the other hand, the range suggests

correlation at short ranges, specifically in the time intervals from 0 to 40 and 65 to 100, indicating greater stiffness in the ascending aorta. There is total correlation in the time interval from 45 to 60, suggesting that blood pressure during the cardiac cycle affects all maximum diameters.

Figure 6. Patient 18: sill and range (top); and aneurysm deformation of the ascending aorta (bottom) throughout the cardiac cycle.

Patient 18 has a large aneurysm and high maximum variability (see sill, Figure 6). Additionally, it has long ranges, indicating that at almost all time intervals, most of the diameters are correlated.

Figure 7. Patient 30: sill and range (top); and aneurysm deformation of the ascending aorta (bottom) throughout the cardiac cycle.

Patient 30 has a small aneurysm with a minor deformation. The maximum variability is not very high, and the ranges are large, indicating that this patient has a more elastic aorta.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an initial approach to analyzing ATAAs using spatial statistics. The findings suggest that spatial statistics can be a valuable tool for identifying patterns in aneurysms, such as their location in the ascending aorta through variograms. However, further exploration is needed to assess the effectiveness of the sill and range parameters in studying elasticity and stiffness.

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